
A Case Study on Homestay Tourism with Reference to Madhya Pradesh Region

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ABSTRACT

Homestay tourism has taken off across the country, establishing itself as an example of tourism innovation and upgradation and attracting growing amounts of cash. The Indian Ministry of Tourism has been investing more in the development of homestay destinations in recent years, which have a profound and long-term socioeconomic impact on rural communities. The government expects that growth in the rural tourist sector, particularly homestay tourism, will help to enhance the socioeconomic development of the communities in the affected areas. It is because homestay tourism is able to take advantage of nature's beauty as well as the community's exquisite customs and cultures as appealing techniques to draw tourists to their village, hence increasing tourism operations in the area. Since its inception, homestay tourism has received such positive feedback that it is now being used as a technique to alleviate poverty in rural communities. Tourists who visit these less-visited areas of the country will have a more intimate and personal experience with the country's unique cultural history. Homestay tourism is a neglected topic in India, despite its growing importance in the domestic tourism sector and its relevance to community-based forms of tourism in general. The goal of this article is to look into the ramifications of effective involvement in Madhya Pradesh homestay tourism. To better steer the growth of homestay tourism, it is necessary to focus on strengthening tourism facilities and the environment, fostering tourism cultural experiences, and increasing the value of tourism services.

Key Words: - Homestay, M.P Tourism, Tourism, Rural, Community.

Introduction

Tourism operations in a given location should be able to assist the local community, notably in terms of lowering poverty rates by creating work possibilities for people like lodge owners, property management agents, and tourist guides, to mention a few. Homestay tourism is increasing, and it's quickly becoming a critical component of tourism development. Homestay tourism is a result of the shift in tourism from a concentration on sightseeing to leisure holidays, and its forms of development are diversifying, deepening, and innovating to meet the expectations of visitors for recreational holiday consumption. Homestay is predicated on increased support for tourism growth, while tourism restructuring and upgrading also require developing tourism forms like homestay. Ecotourism, cultural based tourism, shopping tourism, Fair-festival based tourism, ethnic tourism, art and heritage based tourism, sports tourism, and nature tourism have all been introduced in India for a long time. Many of these tourism ideas have already been combined and declared as the international marketing strategy for tourism products. Because of the constant integration of homestay and tourist, industries connected to homestay tourism are continuously aggregated, and the homestay tourism industry's chain is steadily expanded, fostering the rapid growth of a homestay tourism agglomeration region.

The attractiveness of homestay tourism is a significant manifestation of the shift in tourism from traditional sightseeing to leisure holidays, and the perception of homestay tourism is crucial to understanding tourism transformation and upgrading. Only a few studies have examined the assistance of homestay tourism agglomeration development in the domestic homestay development process, with experience always ahead of theoretical research. The shaping, construction, innovation, development, and protection of natural attractions, tourism planning, and other essential aspects all benefit from study on the degree of support for residential development. As a result, the goal of this study is to determine the amount of support for the growth of homestay tourism from the perspective of tourists' perceived value, in order to adjust to the changing situation of homestay tourism development and to promote quality development in tourist destinations, which itself is gaining theoretical and practical significance.

Rural homestays give visitors a look into the daily lives of village residents, allowing them to interact with the community in ways that are different from traditional tourism interactions and settings (Dole zal, 2011). Travelers looking for a unique experience, personalized care, and genuine social interactions with their hosts will enjoy staying in a homestay (Wang, 2007).

The Concept of Homestay Tourism

Bed & Breakfast / Homestay Scheme in Incredible India, The scheme allows foreign and domestic tourists to stay with an Indian family and experience warm hospitality while learning about Indian culture and cuisine in a safe and affordable environment. This Ministry has reviewed the programme and

streamlined the requirements in order to foster the expansion of such establishments while also making the approval process easier. Through its domestic offices, the Ministry of Tourism has been holding sensitization seminars on the marketing of home stays/Incredible India Bed & Breakfast Establishments in all States. This is a continuous procedure. On December 10, 2018, Incredible India Bed and Breakfast Establishments and Incredible India Homestay Establishments received amended classification and reclassification guidelines. A form of alternative tourism in which visitors stay with the host family in the same home and are immersed in the family's and community's daily lives (ASEAN, Home stay). Homestay is defined as "a situation in which a family opens their home to international students for a portion of or the entirety of their stay in the country." Richardson (2003). Resorts, Apartment, Guest Houses, Bed & Breakfast / Homestay Establishments, Tented Accommodation, Online Travel Aggregators, Stand-alone Air Catering Units, Convention Centers, and Standalone Restaurants are all approved by the Ministry of Tourism under its voluntary programmes.

Madhya Pradesh Home Stay Establishment (Registration and Regulation) Scheme, 2010

(Revised 2018)

Under this scheme, the home owner will be able to provide residential facility to national and international tourists in any part of his residence. Home stay unit can be registered with Madhya Pradesh Tourism Board. Homestay Establishment (Registration and Regulation) Scheme 2010 (revised 2018): The scheme is introduced for providing comfortable home stay facilities to supplement the available accommodation for tourists to experience the reputed Indian hospitality, cuisine, customs and traditions by staying with Indian families. Homestay owner resides in the same premises, and spares a portion of it for homestay facility.

Registration Process

Name Category	Application Fee (GST Additional @18%)
Home Stay	Silver Category - 1000/ Gold Category - 2000/ Diamond Category – 3000

The validity of registration is 3 years.

M.P Tourism Homestay

Homestay is one of the execution tactics that exemplifies the Indian government's tourism development strategy. Here are a few examples:

- Promoting Foreign Currency Exchange
- Promoting social and economic development on an equal footing.
- Building international relationship
- Molding image of India at International level
- Encouraging all ethnic groups to participate in this field
- Promoting Community development
- Increasing the integration of urban and rural areas and cultural exchange.

OPPORTUNITIES FOR HOMESTAYS

Economic Opportunities of Homestay	Social Opportunities of Homestay
Bringing economic and job opportunities to rural communities, hence reducing poverty.	A wonderful venue for intercultural exchanges (guest host interactions)
Promoting tourism investment from both domestic and international sources	Reducing tensions between different races and nationalities
Micro-enterprise development in tourism and its numerous linked industries.	Retention of youths through participation in local opportunities
Direct economic benefits consumption of food, accommodation and purchase of souvenirs.	Locals gain confidence by learning new languages and abilities.
Handicrafts and artisan works are examples of indigenous skills that should be preserved	As modernization advances in, make native's tech aware, "smart," and self-sufficient.

Environmental Opportunities of Homestay	Tourism related Opportunities
As training would be provided, it would be extremely beneficial in lowering common sanitation-related disorders.	Tourists get the opportunity to see natural and cultural variety
Persuading the residents to keep the premises, kitchens, and restrooms, among other things, neat and clean	Increased capacity of the destination's accommodation supply
Environmental conservation is becoming more popular in the host areas.	By advertising the location all year, the problem of seasonality is eliminated.
Obtaining cash for the preservation of the natural environment.	Increase tourism awareness among both domestic and international travelers by involving key stakeholders on a regular basis.

CHALLENGES OF HOMESTAY

- ❖ There are insufficient legal requirements, such as registration of homestays, booking of homestays, and other policies.
- ❖ Due to a lack of education and training institutes, skilled human resources such as guides, entrepreneurs, and hospitality experts are in short supply.
- ❖ Poor infrastructural facilities, such as good roads, transportation, power, healthcare, communication, and other residential facilities, make it difficult to build and promote better service to current and potential homestay visitors.
- ❖ In addition, there is a lack of marketing and promotion of homestay tourism in the country. In the country, there is no suitable organisation for marketing and network expansion.
- ❖ Improper resource management at the location is also a significant obstacle in extending the viability of homestays.
- ❖ Foreign tourists are discouraged from visiting India due to a lack of peace, security, and instability.
- ❖ There is a lack of coordination among various tourist participants, including the government, tourism players, tourism intermediaries, and other non-government organizations involved in homestay tourism.
- ❖ Locals are less aware of the importance of protecting natural and cultural resources. In India, a lack of ecotourism techniques is also a major obstacle to the successful development of homestays.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- ❖ For the local population, there is a need for homestay planning and growth. As a result, the local inhabitants of the proposed homestay tourism location should be given technical assistance in designing and developing homestays.
- ❖ Locals at the homestay tourism location should be provided leadership, hospitality, and food and beverage training so that tourists receive exceptional service.
- ❖ Local people should be given loan subsidies and other fiscal incentives to upgrade their existing facilities, such as beds, rooms, toilets, taps, cleanliness, and so on.
- ❖ The home stay tourist destination should be linked to other tourism stakeholders in the country, and tourism entrepreneurs should promote it as well.
- ❖ Create a community tourism fund in homestay tourism sites to invest in infrastructure and capacity building.
- ❖ Homestay tourism operations, both community and privately run, should be differentiated and treated as such by the government when providing assistance and other services.
- ❖ The building of a homestay tourism database is required so that travelers may simply research, choose, and book their stay.
- ❖ The government could offer public employees a "Leave Travel Concession" and encourage them to participate in homestay tourism.
- ❖ There is a problem of profit sharing among all community members in most homestay tourism sites. As a result, when considering the development of homestay tourism in the area, every member of the community should be included for the benefit sharing method.

The Strategy and Implementation

- Increase the number of job openings and encourage the recruitment of local residents to fill them.
- Give possibilities for local residents to gain experience in the tourism industry through training.
- Give the local community opportunities to work in the commercial sector - for example, the local community can work as a food vendor, a handicrafts manufacturer, or a tourist guide.
- Create community income funds – funds can be obtained through dividends, entrance fees, donations, and profit distributions, to name a few. The fund is collected and used for the process of sustainable development – this strategy can be realised through strong collaboration among residents, corporations, and authorities.

The major goal of these initiatives is to mitigate the community's negative consequences of tourism. Every issue that arises will be dealt with positively, while infrastructure and amenities will be constructed and provided for the residents, as this adds to the improvement of the locals' living standards.

Conclusion

For the development of homestay tourism, the government must set clear development goals as well as specific rules and regulations that will stimulate the growth of the homestay tourism agglomeration region. We should not only have the policy guidance of government departments and reasonable planning in the process of developing homestay tourism, but we should also give benefit to the role of the main body of the market and consider tourist demands, without being either too eager to achieve immediate benefits or too self-contained, so that the policy's role can be played to its full potential. Many villages in India have started Homestay initiatives to reduce the challenges connected with traditional tourism in response to increased demand for alternative types of tourism among international tourists and an increasing domestic middle class. The importance of homestay in Madhya Pradesh is highlighted in this research.

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Homestay in Madhya pradesh					
No.	Homestay	Address	No.	Homestay	Address
1	Salban Homestay	Birsa	37	Orchha Best Homestay	Orchha
2	Artistic Homestay	Bhopal	38	Sitamadi Homestay	Orchha
3	Natures Courtyard Homestay	Bhopal	39	Shree ram Homestay	Orchha
4	Baniyan Tree Farms	Bhopal	40	Athiti Homestay	Orchha
5	Geeteshvram Homestay	Bhopal	41	Rudraani kala gram	Orchha
6	Holiday Homes and Resort	Bhopal	42	Comfort & Cozy Homestay	Orchha
7	Gioavnni Suites	Bhopal	43	Amma Homestay	Orchha
8	Fahad Guest House	Bhopal	44	Mridul Homestay	Orchha
9	Mahua Homestay	Bhopal	45	Aaradhya homestay	Orchha
10	Bhopal Lake view Homestay	Bhopal	46	Karnavati Homestay	Madla
11	Colonels Corner Homestay	Bhopal	47	Aryan camp Homestay	Panna
12	Prem Homestay	Chhatarpur	48	Sagar Estate Homestay	Sagar
13	Pandit Homestay	Gwalior	49	Kila the heritage palace	satna
14	Aaramgah Homestay	Hoshangabad	50	Vijay kadambari house	Maihar
15	Raj Vihar Homesaty	Hoshangabad	51	Palash villa Homestay	Seoni
16	Jain Residency	Hoshangabad	52	Trolet Inn	Ujjain
17	Narmada Nirman Jaivik upwan	Budhni	53	Skays Camp Homestay	Umariya
18	Gokul Homestay	Indore	54	Maharaja Homestay	Orchha

19	Vaikunth Homestay	Indore	55	Bundeli farm Homestay	Niwari
20	Maninder's Homestay	Indore	56	Evelyns Homestay	Panchmari
21	Home away from Home	Indore	57	Mrignayani Homestay	Panchmari
22	Ashta lakshmi Tourist homestay	Indore	58	Panarpani Farm stay	Pagara
23	NPS Enterprises	Indore	59	The Satpura Panchtatava villa	Hoshangabad
24	Krishna Homestay	Indore	60	Shiv Homestay	Panchmari
25	Stay with the chef	Indore	61	Krishna Residency	Panchmari
26	Stay 10 Homestay	Indore	62	Aashirwad Regency	Bhopal
27	Motel Check Inn	Indore	63	laal Kothi Homestay	Bhopal
28	The Green Meadow	Jabalpur	64	Induprabha Homestay	Dhar
29	Jaiswal Homestay	Jabalpur	65	Happy hour Homestay	Jabalpur
30	Indraprasth Homestay	Jhabua	66	Naulana Homestay	Indore
31	Relax Homestay	Khargaon	67	Shri Sitaram Homestay	Orchha
32	The Bliss celebration of homestay	Khargaon	68	Sukriti farm villa	Bhopal
33	Gharonda Homestay	Mandla	69	Wow Rooms Homestay	Jabalpur
34	Shri Rambhajan	Vangram	70	Gracevilla Farmstay	Mandla
35	Courtyard House	Mandla	71	Blue Lagoon	Bhopal
36	Happy Family Homestay	Orchha			